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Research Article

**STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD
DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR ESTIMATION OF
DOLUTEGRAVIR IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL
DOSAGE FORM****Hrutik Kanhed^{1*}, Prof. Sunil S Bhagat², Prof. J.P Ambhore³, Dr. V. S. Aadha⁴**
^{1*4} Dr. Rajendra Gode College of Pharmacy, Malkapur, Maharashtra- 443101**Abstract:**

To quantify dolutegravir in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form through forced degradation tests by RP-HPLC chromatographic method. Dolutegravir was extracted chromatographically at a Finapak C8 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) reverse-phase analytical column with 06 min analytical run time. The mobile phase consisted ratio of 50:50 v/v mixture of methanol and phosphate buffer. The detection wavelength was set to 220 nm and the mobile phase was streamed at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The mobile phase was used as diluent. The Injection volume was 20 μg/ml. Retention time 3.907 minutes was discovered. It was determined that dolutegravir's linearity limit fell between 0.998. It was discovered that the limits of detection and quantification were, respectively 0.9576 and 2.9018. The method proposed can be helpful in the quality control test of bulk and mixed dose forms of dolutegravir, according to the results obtained from the validation parameters. It was observed that dolutegravir showed high degradation in oxidation as it was up to 74% and showed less degradation in Alkali, Acid, and Photolytic Degradation. It was seen that degradation studies showed a well-resolved peak. The method represents a fast-analytical procedure and stability indicating analytical method for the estimation of Dolutegravir in bulk and its dosage forms. The approach is fast, accurate, repeatable, and specific, according to validation studies. The technique can be used to precisely and accurately analyse a large number of samples regularly.

KEYWORDS: RP-HPLC, Dolutegravir, Method Development, Method Validation, ICH, Stability Studies.**Corresponding author:****Hrutik Kanhed,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Dolutegravir is known as (4R,12aS)-N-(2,4-difluorobenzyl)-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6,8-dioxo-3,4,6,8,12,12a-hexahydro-2H-pyrido[1',2':4,5]pyrazino[2,1-b][1,3]oxazine-carboxamide.^[1-3] A class of antiretroviral medications called dolutegravir is authorized for the treatment of HIV (human immune deficiency virus). One type of antiretroviral medication that targets the viral integrase is dolutegravir, often known as an integrase inhibitor.^[4-8] Dolutegravir is only permitted to be taken in conjunction with other antiretroviral medications. An effective treatment for human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) infection is dolutegravir, an integrase strand transfer inhibitor (INSTI).^[9-14] The HIV enzyme integrase catalyses the transfer of viral genetic material into human chromosomes. Dolutegravir is an orally accessible medication that binds to this location. This enzyme stops integrase from attaching to retroviral deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), which is necessary for the HIV replication cycle, and so hinders the strand transfer phase.^[15-19] This enzyme is in charge of stopping the replication of HIV-1. Its molecular weight is 419.38 g/mol and its chemical formula is C₂₀H₁₉F₂N₃O₅. Dolutegravir (DTG) is an antiretroviral drug that is used in combination with other medications to treat HIV/AIDS. It is marketed under the trade name Tivicay.^[20-24]

FIG.1. Chemical structure of Dolutegravir

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Instrumentation

Chromatography was performed with Shimadzu HPLC provided with sampler, column oven, degasser and PDA detector. The data was acquired through LC lab solution software.

Chemicals and Reagents

Pure samples of Dolutegravir were obtained from Emcure Pharmaceuticals Hyderabad, Telangana. The commercial samples of the tablets 'Instgra' containing Dolutegravir 50 mg were provided by Emcure Pharmaceuticals LTD store. All the chemicals were HPLC grade purchased from Loba

chemie. HPLC grade methanol, water and all other chemicals were obtained from Loba chemie.

Preparation of mobile phase

Phosphate Buffer [PH 4.5] and Methanol taken in the ratio 50:50 v/v mixed well and sonicate to degas.

Chromatographic Conditions

Shimadzu HPLC system and PDA Shimadzu (SPD-M20A) detector were used for Chromatographic separation. The chromatographic column utilized in the study was Finepak C8 (4.6 × 250 mm, 5µm). Different mobile phases were tried, and the one containing Methanol: Phosphate Buffer (pH 4.5) in the ratio of 50:50 % v/v was appropriate. The mobile phase was subjected to vacuum filtration by using a 0.45 µm filter. The mobile phase was used as a diluent. The flow rate selected was 1.0ml/min. All the determinations were performed at a constant column temperature (Ambient) and an injection volume was 20µg/ml. The Dolutegravir showed absorbance maxima at 220 nm.

Preparation of Phosphate buffer (pH4.5)

Phosphate buffer was prepared by weighing 2.95 grams of KH₂PO₄ and 5.45 grams of K₂HPO₄, dissolved and diluted to 1000ml with HPLC water. The Orthophosphoric acid was added to maintain the pH level at 4.5.

Preparation of Standard Solution

Accurately weighed 50 mg standard Dolutegravir weighed and powdered, average weight equivalent to 50 mg of dolutegravir transferred to 50 ml volumetric flask and dissolve in 10 ml Dimethyl sulfoxide and volume was make up to final volume with diluent (methanol) to get solution with concentration of 1mg/ml of Dolutegravir respectively. From this stock solution, pipette out 1ml of solution into 10 ml volumetric flask, make up the volume with diluent to get stock solution with concentration of 100 µg/ml.

Preparation of Sample Solutions

Aliquots of 0.5, 1, 1.5 2, 2.5, 3, 4, and 5 ml were pipette out from the above stock solutions and transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was make up with diluents. 5, 10,15, 20, 25, 30, 40, and 50 µg/ml of Dolutegravir respectively.

Assay

Procedure:

20 tablets were weighed and powdered and average weight equivalent to 50 mg of dolutegravir transferred to 50 ml volumetric flask and dissolve in 10 ml Dimethyl sulfoxide, volume was made up to final volume with diluent and sonicated for 15 min.

Following filtering, a solution comprising 1000 µg/ml of Dolutegravir was obtained. Dolutegravir was made with final quantity of 20 µg/ml from the above-mentioned solution.

20 µg/ml of standard and sample solutions were injected into the injector of HPLC, and the peak areas of the drugs in standard and sample were compared and the assay was performed. Dolutegravir show the purity percentage values of 99.85 % w/v respectively.

Method Validation

Specificity

It was confirmed by injecting the placebo (Talc, Magnesium Stearate, Starch, Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose, Colloidal silicon dioxide and Sodium starch glycolate) and placebo spiked standard and observed that there was no shift in wavelength interference due to placebo. This confirms the specificity of the proposed method. [25,26]

System suitability test

The system suitability test of the method was carried out by injecting six replicate standard solution of Dolutegravir System suitability parameters like percentage relative standard deviation (% RSD), USP tailing factors (T), USP plate count (N), resolution, tailing factor, No. of theoretical plates were calculated. [27,28]

Validation of Proposed method

The developed method was validated as per the ICH (International Conference Harmonization) guidelines with respect to System suitability, Precision, Specificity, Forced degradation studies, Linearity, Accuracy, Limit of detection and Limit of quantification. [29,30]

Linearity

Aliquots of 0.5,1,1.5,2, 2.5, 3, 4 and 5 ml were taken in 10 ml volumetric flask from stock solution of 100 mg/ml Dolutegravir and then diluted up to mark with diluent. concentration of 10,20,30,40,50 ppm Each level was injected into the chromatographic system and peak area was measured. A graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak was plotted and the correlation coefficient calculated.

Precision

Method precision

The reliability of process was confirmed through six sequential injections of the Dolutegravir.

Intra-Day Precision and Inter-day Precision

To check the inter-day and intra-day variations of the method, the solutions containing 20 µg/ml Dolutegravir were subjected to the proposed HPLC method of analysis on different days and the results obtained were noted.

Accuracy

Recovery studies were employed to assess the analytical method's accuracy. Workplace-spiked Dolutegravir working standards were then made up with a diluent that produced the desired Dolutegravir concentrations of 80 µg/ml, 100 µg/ml, and 120 µg/ml. For Dolutegravir samples, the amount obtained was assessed, the recovery % and mean recovery values were determined.

Robustness

It was performed by changing the HPLC pump flow rate variations ± 0.2 ml/min and organic composition of the mobile phase ±5%.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness was assessed by repeating the experiment with various variables, including different analysts. Under typical, expected operating circumstances, test results were consistent within the laboratory and amongst analysts. Analysts I and II separately prepared the Dolutegravir reference solution using a diluent by the test process. Six injections of 20 µg/ml of these solutions were made, and for Analysts I and II, the percentage RSD for the Peak region of the six replicate injections was computed.

Limit of Detection

LOD's can be calculated using the response standard deviation (σ) and the calibration curve slope (S).

Formula:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Limit of Quantification

LOQ's can be calculated using the response standard deviation (σ) and the calibration curve slope (S).

Formula:

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Force Degradation Studies

Oxidation Degradation Studies

Sample solution of Dolutegravir, 1 ml of 3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was added. The solution was kept for 30 min at 60°C and cooled to room temperature and finally made up to volume with diluent, sample solution was injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Alkali Degradation studies

1 ml of stock solution of Dolutegravir and 1 ml of 2N sodium hydroxide solution was added and refluxed for 30 min at 60°C and cooled to room temperature and finally made up to volume with diluent, sample solution was injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Acid Degradation studies

1 ml of stock solution of Dolutegravir and 1 ml of 2N Hydrochloric acid was added and refluxed for 30 min at 60°C and cooled to room temperature and finally made up to volume with diluent, sample solution was injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

Photolytic Degradation studies

The photochemical stability of the drug was also studied by exposing the sample stock solution to UV Light by keeping the beaker in UV Chamber for one day in photo stability chamber. For HPLC study, the resultant solution was diluted, sample solution was injected into the system and the chromatograms were recorded to assess the stability of sample.

20 µg/ml of the acidic, basic, oxidative and photo stability solutions were injected. The peak area for the Dolutegravir were measured and % degradation was calculated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In this study, endeavors were made to create and validate a simple, reliable, quick, precise, and

stability-indicating method for the HPLC determination of dolutegravir in bulk and their pharmaceutical formulations. In RP-HPLC method, the analyte was resolved using Methanol: Phosphate Buffer (PH 4.5) (50:50 v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min, on Simple Binary Gradient HPLC pump. PDA detector with Data LC solution Software and C8 column (4.6 x 250 mm). The detection was carried out at 220 nm. The peak of Dolutegravir were found at 3.943. Method gave the good resolution and suitable retention time. The recovery for Dolutegravir was determined to be 100.01, 100.05 and 100.45, demonstrating the efficacy of the suggested technique. Dolutegravir showed linearity in the concentration range of 10-50 %, with a drug regression of 0.9998. Dolutegravir limit of detection and limit of quantification were found to be 0.9576 µg/ml and 2.9018 µg/ml, respectively. It was observed that dolutegravir show high degradation in oxidation as it was up to 74% and show less degradation in Alkali, Acid and Photolytic Degradation. It was seen that degradation studies showed well resolve peak. Hence, this Method is Stability Indicating Method. The analysis's findings across the board were verified in terms of range, linearity, precision, ruggedness, and accuracy. It was discovered that the procedures were also economical, rapid reliable, sensitive, and consistent. It was discovered that the procedure was simple, exact, accurate, accessible, and repeatable. So, the recommended approach can be applied to the regular quality control assessment of dolutegravir in both tablet and bulk medication forms.

Fig.2. Optimized chromatographic condition

Specificity

No elution of the interfering peak takes place, which shows that the peak of the analyte was pure and excipients in the combination should not interfere with the analyte. No interference was observed at the retention time for the respective drug. Therefore, the method is selective for the determination of Dolutegravir. This confirms the specificity of the proposed method.

Linearity and Range

It was evaluated by visual inspection of the plot of peak area as a function of analyte concentrations for Dolutegravir. The results are reported in table 1. The calibration curves are shown from the linearity studies, the specified range was determined for Dolutegravir as 10 - 50 µg/ml respectively. The Correlation Coefficient for Dolutegravir was found to be within the acceptance criteria of 0.998. The linearity results for Dolutegravir in the specified concentration range are found satisfactory. The approach is specific in determining dolutegravir. This validates the suggested method's specificity.

Conc.	Area
10	5400241
20	10301656
30	15255364
40	20451110
50	25633625

Table 1. Linearity results for dolutegravir**Fig.3. Calibration Curve of dolutegravir.****Precision****Method Precision**

The % R.S.D of peak area was 0.33261, It showed that the drug was having good precision and the % R.S.D of peak area, retention time, U.S.P Plate count and U.S.P tailing were present within the Acceptance criteria of R.S.D < 2 %. The results are reported in table 2.

Sr.No.	Peak area
1	10301656
2	10321765
3	10342879
4	10371657
5	10390711
6	10374836
Mean	10350584
SD	34427.48
%RSD	0.33261

Table.2. Repeatability

System Suitability

The parameters including resolution, tailing factor, no. of theoretical plates mainly used to assess system suitability. The Tailing factor for Dolutegravir was found to be 1.035 respectively. The Theoretical plates per unit for Dolutegravir was found to be 3642 respectively. The tailing factor values for Dolutegravir indicated the symmetrical nature of the peak. System suitability results are presented in table 3.

Sr.No.	Drug name	Peak area	Retention time	Theoretical plate	Tailing factor
1	Dolutegravir	10301656	3.902	3642	1.035
2	Dolutegravir	10321765	3.906	3659	1.033
3	Dolutegravir	10342879	3.907	3698	1.038
4	Dolutegravir	10371657	3.905	3543	1.243
5	Dolutegravir	10390711	3.903	3798	1.131
6	Dolutegravir	10321765	3.904	3467	1.234

Table.3. System Suitability

Accuracy

The Mean recovery of 80 µg/ml, 100 µg/ml and 120 µg/ml for Dolutegravir were found to be 99.95%, 99.83 % and 100.17 % respectively. The obtained mean recovery values were within the acceptance criteria of 98 - 102 %. The results are reported in table 4. This serves as a good index of the accuracy and reproducibility of the proposed method. This shows that the method was accurate.

%Level	Concentration Added (µg/ml)	%Recovery	Mean	SD	%RSD
80 %	36	99.95	99.95	0.06	0.060
	36	100.01			
	36	99.89			
100 %	40	99.86	99.83	0.02	0.025
	40	99.81			
	40	99.84			
120 %	44	100.01	100.17	0.24	0.242
	44	100.05			
	44	100.45			

Table.4. Accuracy data for dolutegravir

Robustness

U.S.P Plate count and U.S.P tailing were found to be 3470 and 1.359 for 0.5 ml/min flow rate of Dolutegravir. U.S.P Plate count and U.S.P tailing were found to be 3698 and 1.243 for 1.0 ml/min flow rate of Dolutegravir. U.S.P Plate count and U.S.P tailing were found to be 3989 and 1.568 for 5% less organic composition in mobile phase for Dolutegravir. U.S.P Plate count and U.S.P tailing were found to be 3998 and 1.879 for 5% more organic composition in mobile phase for Dolutegravir. The method was robust even by the

change in the Mobile phase ratio $\pm 5\%$ and flow rate ± 0.2 ml/min. The obtained U.S.P Plate count and U.S.P tailing factor values are very close with actual flow rate and mobile phase composition. On the evaluation of the results, it can be concluded that the variation in $\pm 5\%$ of organic composition in the mobile phase and flow rate ± 0.2 ml/min affected the method significantly. Hence it indicates that the method is robust even by the change in the mobile phase $\pm 5\%$ and flow rate ± 0.2 ml/min. The chromatograms are shown in (Figure 4 - 7) and results are reported in table 5.

Fig.4. Chromatogram showing robustness solution of increased mobile phase flowrate (1.5 ml/min) of Dolutegravir

Sr. No	Parameters	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Actual method	3642	1.035
2	Changes in the flow rate (0.5 ml/min)	3878	1.236
3	Changes in the flow rate (1.5 ml/min)	3889	1.541
4	Changes in the Organic phase composition in the mobile phase (5 % less)	3542	1.674
5	Changes in the Organic phase composition in the mobile phase (5 % more)	3998	1.879

Table.5. Results of the robustness study for dolutegravir.

Ruggedness

The R.S.D % of Peak area for Analyst I and Analyst II was found to be 0.060 and 0.247 for Dolutegravir. The R.S.D % of peak area was present within the acceptance criteria of R.S.D < 2 %. RSD % values for ruggedness indicated that the method is rugged and does not show variations in the results when performed by different analysts. The results are reported in table 6.

Parameters	% RSD Peak Area Dolutegravir
Analyst I	0.060
Analyst II	0.247

Table.6. Ruggedness data for dolutegravir

Limit of Detection

The LOD of Dolutegravir were 0.9576 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The obtained LOD values were very less when compared to the reported method. As per the analytical point of view, the method could detect least quantity. So, when compared to the reported methods the developed method is most suitable to detect less quantity.

Limit of Quantification

The LOQ of Dolutegravir were 2.9081 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The obtained LOQ values were very less when compared to reported methods. As per the analytical point of view, the method could detect least quantity. So, when compared to the reported methods the developed method is most suitable to quantify less quantity.

Degradation Studies

Degradation studies were carried out as per ICH guidelines. The sample solutions were subjected to acidic, basic, peroxide and light. It was observed that dolutegravir show high degradation in oxidation as it was up to 74% and

show less degradation in Alkali, Acid and Photolytic Degradation. It was seen that degradation studies showed well resolve peak. Hence the developed method can be used for quality control analysis and accelerated stability studies. The obtained data are reported in table 7. The chromatograms are shown in (Figure 8 – 11).

Sr.No.	Degradation Condition	% Drug Undegraded	% Drug Degraded
1	Oxidation	25.8369	74.1601
2	Alkali	88.0279	11.9721
3	Acid	95.0408	4.9592
4	Photolytic	88.1476	11.8524

Table.7. Results of degradation studies for dolutegravir

Fig.5. Chromatogram showing robustness solution of decreased mobile phase flowrate (0.5 ml/min) of dolutegravir

Fig.6. Chromatogram showing robustness solution of more organic phase ratio of mobile phase (+5 %) of dolutegravir

Fig.7. Chromatogram showing robustness solution of less organic phase ratio of mobile phase (-5 %) of dolutegravir

Fig.8. Chromatogram showing oxidative degradation for Dolutegravir

Fig.9. Chromatogram showing Alkali degradation for Dolutegravir**Fig.11. Chromatogram showing Photo stability degradation for Dolutegravir****CONCLUSION:**

An examination of the literature found that there is presently no method accessible for assessing individual medications in dose form. The goal of the current work was to create a suitable, sensitive, and straightforward RP-HPLC method for estimating individual medicines in their dose form. In RP-HPLC method, the analyte was resolved using Methanol: Phosphate Buffer (PH 4.5) (50:50 v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min, on Simple Binary Gradient HPLC pump. PDA detector with Data LC solution Software and C8 column (4.6 x 250 mm). The detection was carried out at 220 nm. The peak of Dolutegravir were found at 3.943. Method gave the good resolution and suitable retention time. The recovery for Dolutegravir was determined to be 100.01, 100.05 and 100.45,

demonstrating the efficacy of the suggested technique.

Dolutegravir showed linearity in the concentration range of 10-15 %, with a drug regression of 0.9998. Dolutegravir limit of detection and limit of quantification were found to be 0.9576 µg/ml and 2.9018 µg/ml, respectively.

It was observed that dolutegravir show high degradation in oxidation as it was up to 74% and show less degradation in Alkali, Acid and Photolytic Degradation. It was seen that degradation studies showed well resolve peak. Hence, this Method is Stability Indicating Method. The analysis's findings across the board were verified in terms of range, linearity, precision, ruggedness, and accuracy. It was

discovered that the procedures were also economical, rapid reliable, sensitive, and consistent. It was discovered that the procedure was simple, exact, accurate, accessible, and repeatable. So, the recommended approach can be applied to the regular quality control assessment of dolutegravir in both tablet and bulk medication forms.

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